

Some Sulphur Derivatives of 2-Methoxytoluene.

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Meldrum and Shah (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1992), while sulphonating 2-methoxytoluene with 3% fuming sulphuric acid, obtained an alkali-insoluble by-product (m.p. 138°) containing sulphur; they did not, however, investigate its nature. Zehenter (*Monatsh.*, 1912, 33, 335) also obtained a by-product of a similar type during the sulphonation of 2-hydroxytoluene with 8% fuming sulphuric acid; he, however, recognised the product as a sulphone but did not investigate its precise constitution. The by-product from 2-methoxytoluene must evidently be a sulphone and the authors' first objective was to determine the constitution of both the above products.

The sulphonation method gives a very poor yield of the sulphone. The large quantity of the product, required for the purpose of determining its constitution, could, however, be obtained by the general synthetical method of Beckurts and Otto (*Ber.*, 1878, 11, 472). The product, obtained by the action of 2-methoxytoluene-5-sulphonylchloride on 2-methoxytoluene, was found to be identical with that obtained by the sulphonation method. This synthesis, however, does not throw much light on the position of the SO₂-group with respect to the constituents in the other benzene residue in the sulphone.

The method of decomposing the sulphone with phosphorus pentachloride (Meyer and Jacobson, "Lehrbuch der Organischen Chemie, 1921, Vol. II, Part I, p. 144) and the method of decomposing the sulphone with sodium in a suitable solvent (Krafft and Worster, *Ber.*, 1893, 26, 1813) failed in eliciting the constitution of the sulphone. It was, however, thought that by oxidising the above sulphone to the corresponding dibasic acid and removing the two carboxyl groups, the resulting sulphone could possibly be identified with a known compound. This proved to be the case, and the sulphone (III) obtained by these reactions was identified as *p*-anisolsulphone, m.p. 129° (Mauthner, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 3593; also Smiles and Le-Rossignol, *J.*

Chem. Soc., 1908, 93, 756). The constitution of the original sulphone must therefore be represented as (I).

By demethylating the sulphone (I), 4:4'-dihydroxy-3:3'-dimethyl-diphenylsulphone (m.p. 263°) was obtained. This, therefore, must be the constitution of Zehenter's sulphone which is stated to melt at 263-65°.

The synthesis of the following new sulphones from 2-methoxytoluene and various sulphonylchlorides are found to verify the general rules of substitution; that the sulphonyl group takes up the *para*-position (or *ortho*, depending upon the original substituents present) to a methoxy or ethoxy group. But an exception to this rule is found in the cases of anisol and phenetol:

(a) Benzenesulphonylchloride and 2-methoxytoluene gave a sulphone identical with that obtained from benzene and 2-methoxytoluene-5-sulphonylchloride. Hence the product is 3-methyl-4-methoxydiphenylsulphone.

(b) *p*-Toluenesulphonylchloride and 2-methoxytoluene gave a sulphone identical with that obtained, as the sole product, from toluene and 2-methoxytoluene-5-sulphonylchloride. Hence the product is 3:4-dimethyl-4-methoxydiphenylsulphone.

(c) *p*-Anisolsulphonylchloride and 2-methoxytoluene gave a sulphone (m.p. 126°) identical with that obtained from anisol and 2-methoxytoluene-5-sulphonylchloride. Hence this product must be 3-methyl-4:4'-dimethoxydiphenylsulphone. But in the second method, along with the usual product (*para*), an isomeric compound (m.p. 102°) was isolated in an appreciable quantity. This was found to be different from the *ortho*-modification which, when synthesised from *o*-anisolsulphonylchloride and 2-methoxytoluene, melted at 145°.

(d) The reactions between (i) 2-methoxytoluene-5-sulphonylchloride and phenetol, and (ii) *p*-anisolsulphonylchloride and anisol were

also found to produce two isomeric compounds in each case. The nature of the second isomeric products is under investigation. The oxidation and demethylation products of many of the above compounds have also been described.

Some other Sulphur Derivatives of 2-Methoxytoluene.

The sulphoxide, sulphonium chloride, sulphide, sulphinic acid, disulphoxide, disulphide, disulphone and the thiol derivatives of 2-methoxytoluene are unknown, although the corresponding derivatives of *m*- and *p*-cresol methyl ether have been described (Smiles, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 2249; Smiles and Le-Rossignol, *loc.cit.*; Hilditch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 1000). Accordingly we have prepared the above derivatives, an account of which will be found in the experimental.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Methoxytoluene-5-sulphonylchloride.—2-Methoxytoluene (62 g.) was gradually added to chlorosulphonic acid (325 g.) in a flask maintained at 0° during the addition. The mixture was kept at 0° for an hour and then poured over crushed ice when the solid sulphonylchloride immediately separated out. When allowed to stand overnight, along with the solid crust of the sulphonylchloride, some flocculent precipitate was also obtained. This was purified and identified as 3:3'-dimethyl-4:4'-dimethoxydiphenylsulphone, m. p. 138° (yield, 2.5%). The sulphonylchloride (yield, 80%) formed hexagonal plates from ether and yielded an amide, m.p. 137° (*cf.* Bromwell, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1897, 19, 573).

3:3'-Dimethyl-4:4'-dimethoxydiphenylsulphone (I).—2-Methoxytoluene-5-sulphonylchloride (11 g.) and 2-methoxytoluene (10 g. excess) in 30 c.c. of carbon disulphide were gradually treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (7 g.) under reflux and then kept overnight. Next day the contents were heated on a water-bath for two hours, the carbon disulphide was removed and the residue decomposed successively by ice-cold water and concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c. c.). The mixture was steam-distilled and the residue washed with ether (yield, 13.8 g.). It formed long needles from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 138°. (Found: C, 62.9; H 5.4; S, 10.64. M. W. (cryoscopic), 306.3. C₁₆H₁₈O₄S requires C, 62.74; H, 5.88; S, 10.46 per cent. M.W., 306).

3:3'-Dicarboxy-4:4'-dimethoxydiphenylsulphone (II).—The finely powdered sulphone (I, 7.5 g.) was suspended in two litres of water containing potassium hydroxide (3 g.) and potassium permanganate (15.5 g.) in solution. The mixture was boiled until it was decolourised, separated from the precipitated manganese dioxide and the filtrate neutralised with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The precipitate (3.5 g.) separated from alcohol as small granular crystals which sintered at 245° and melted at 250° (decomp.).

The unoxidised material could be removed from the precipitated manganese dioxide by extracting with acetic acid. (Found: C, 52.11; H, 4.1; S, 8.55; equiv. 182.8. $C_{16}H_{14}O_8S$ requires C, 52.45; H, 3.82; S, 8.74 per cent., equiv., 188).

Decarboxylation of above: Formation of 4:4'-Dimethoxydiphenylsulphone (III).—The acid (3 g.), mixed with an equal quantity of quicklime, was distilled from a hard glass-bulbed tube. The distillate, a thick yellowish-red liquid, solidified when treated with a little ether (yield, 0.3 g.). It formed stout needles from alcohol, m. p. 129°. The mixed m. p. of this substance with that prepared by Smiles's method (*loc. cit.*) did not change. (Found: C, 60.14; H, 4.74; S, 11.57. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4S$ requires C, 60.43; H, 5.04; S, 11.51 per cent.).

3:3'-Dimethyl-4:4'-dihydroxydiphenylsulphone.—The sulphone (I, 1 g.) was heated with hydriodic acid (10 c. c. *d* 1.7) at 165° under reflux for two hours. The product was successively treated with concentrated alkali and dilute hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in small cubes, m. p. 263° (corr.); yield quantitative. (Found: C, 59.93; H, 4.67; S, 11.42. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4S$ requires C, 60.43; H, 5.04; S, 11.51 per cent.).

3:3'-Dicarboxy-4:4'-dihydroxydiphenylsulphone.—The dibasic acid (II, 0.4 g.) was demethylated with hydriodic acid (5 c. c.) and the phenolic compound crystallised from water in short silky needles, m. p. 306.7° (decomp.). (Found: S, 10.0. $C_{14}H_{10}O_8S$ requires S, 9.47 per cent.).

3-Methyl-4-methoxydiphenylsulphone was prepared in two ways:

(a) Benzenesulphonylchloride and 2-methoxytoluene (in molecular proportions) gave an yield of 75%. (b) 2-Methoxytoluene-5-sulphonylchloride reacting with benzene gave 80% yield; m. p. 112-112.5°. (Found: C, 63.96; H, 5.55; S, 11.8. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3S$ requires C, 64.12; H, 5.32; S, 12.2 per cent.).

3-*Methyl-4-hydroxydiphenylsulphone* was obtained by demethylating the above sulphone with hydriodic acid at 170°. It formed microscopic needles from alcohol, m. p. 226°. (Found: S, 13·25. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3S$ requires S, 12·9 per cent.).

On oxidising the sulphone, m. p. 112°, with alkaline permanganate, 3-*carboxy-4-methoxydiphenylsulphone* was obtained (yield, 33%). It separated as long needles from hot water, m. p. 176°. (Found: S, 11·02; equiv., 292·82. $C_{14}H_{12}O_5S$ requires S, 10·95 per cent.; equiv., 292).

The above sulphone, on demethylation at 155-160°, formed 3-*carboxy-4-hydroxydiphenylsulphone*, which crystallised from hot water in stout needles, m. p. 216-17°. (Found: S, 11·62; equiv., 277·68. $C_{13}H_{10}O_5S$ requires S, 11·51 per cent. equiv., 278).

3: 4'-*Dimethyl-4-methoxydiphenylsulphone* was prepared in two ways: (a) From *p*-toluenesulphonylchloride and 2-methoxytoluene (yield 90%) and (b) from 2-methoxytoluene-5-sulphonylchloride and toluene (yield, 70%). The substance forms thin prismatic plates from alcohol, m. p. 109·5-110°. (Found: C, 64·99; H, 5·92; S, 11·3. $C_{15}H_{16}O_3S$ requires C, 65·21; H, 5·79; S, 11·59 per cent.).

3: 4'-*Dimethyl-4-hydroxydiphenylsulphone* was obtained from the above sulphone by demethylation at 175°. It formed short needles from alcohol, m. p. 200-201°. (Found: S, 12·5. Calc., S, 12·2 per cent.)

3: 4'-*Dicarboxy-4-methoxydiphenylsulphone*.—The sulphone (m. p. 110°) on oxidation with alkaline permanganate yielded the above compound which formed small granular crystals from alcohol, m. p. 283° (yield, 83%). (Found: S, 9·48; equiv., 169·05. Calc., S, 9·52 per cent.; equiv., 168).

4: 4'-*Dimethoxy-3-methyldiphenylsulphone* was prepared in two ways as before: (a) *p*-anisolsulphonylchloride and 2-methoxytoluene gave the sulphone, m. p. 126° (yield 80%). (b) Anisol and 2-methoxytoluene-5-sulphonylchloride gave a mixture of two compounds (total yield, 90%), one of which was identical with the preceding sulphone, m. p. 126°. The isomer, which formed about one third of the product, melted at 102°. (Found for substance, m. p. 126°: C, 61·15; H, 5·55; S, 11·17. Found for substance, m. p. 102°: C, 61·24; H, 5·79; S, 11·26. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4S$ requires C, 61·64; H, 5·48; S, 10·96 per cent.).

3-Carboxy-4: 4'-dimethoxydiphenylsulphone was obtained by oxidising the sulphone (m. p. 126°, 4.5 g.) with alkaline permanganate (4.9 g.) (yield 30%), m. p. 186-7°. (Found: S, 9.61; equiv., 321.8. Calc., S, 9.96 per cent., equiv., 322).

3'-Methyl-2': 4-dimethoxydiphenylsulphone was prepared by the action of *o*-anisolsulphonylchloride (m. p. 55°, prepared by Gattermann's reactions—*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 1153) on 2-methoxytoluene. It formed thin plates or short needles from alcohol, m. p. 145°. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 5.55; S, 10.94. Calc., C, 61.64; H, 5.48; S, 10.96 per cent.).

3: 3'-Dimethyl 4: 4'-dimethoxydiphenylsulphoxide.—Anhydrous aluminium chloride was gradually dissolved in 2-methoxytoluene (20 g. each), and the mixture, saturated with sulphur dioxide below 15°, was treated according to Smiles and Le-Rossignol's method. But of the three possible compounds as suggested by them, only two (sulphoxide and sulphonium chloride) were formed. The sulphoxide, extracted from the acid-liquid with ether, was crystallised from ethyl acetate in colourless rhombic plates, m. p. 87-87.5° (yield, 5.5 g.). On oxidation with alkaline permanganate, it gives the sulphone, m. p. 138° (I). (Found: C, 65.95; H, 6.27; S, 11.4. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3S$ requires C, 66.2; H, 6.2; S, 11.08 per cent.).

*Tri-*o*-cresylsulphonium Chloride*.—The original acid-liquid, after extraction with ether, was extracted with chloroform which on evaporation gave the sulphonium chloride as a semisolid mass; it crystallised from water in colourless plates (yield, 8.5 g.). When recrystallised from acetone two isomeric compounds were obtained:—Fraction I (2 g.), m. p. 140-141°, was more soluble in cold water, but less soluble in cold or hot acetone than the other. (Found: S, 7.89. $C_{24}H_{27}O_3S$ requires S, 7.44 per cent.). Fraction II (6 g.) when recrystallised from moist acetone gave thick plates, m. p. 69-70°, containing three molecules of water of crystallisation. (Found: H_2O , 11.54. $C_{24}H_{27}O_3S$, $3H_2O$ requires H_2O , 11.09 per cent. (For anhydrous salt) S, 7.84. $C_{24}H_{27}O_3S$ requires S, 7.45 per cent.).

3: 3'-Dimethyl-4: 4'-dimethoxydiphenylsulphide was obtained by the reduction of the sulphoxide with zinc dust and glacial acetic acid. The ether extract left a thick liquid on evaporation which gradually solidified after a week; m. p. 37.5-38°. (Found: S, 11.69. Calc., S, 11.67 per cent.).

2-Methoxytoluene-5-sulphinic Acid.—2-Methoxytoluene-5-sulphonyl chloride (5 g.) was reduced by means of sodium sulphite (18 g. in 70 c. c. water) with occasional addition of a little caustic soda solution. The liquid was filtered from the insoluble solid (*A*, granular crystals from benzene, m. p. 206·5° decomp.) and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid when a turbid solution was obtained. This on keeping deposited an oil (3·85 g.). It could not be purified by distillation—even under reduced pressure—as it quickly decomposes on warming. Moreover it spontaneously changes into a white solid (*B*) insoluble in alkali, m. p. 118°. The *sodium* salt (thin leaflets from absolute alcohol) and *silver* salt (short needles from hot water) were prepared and analysed. (Found: Na, 10·8. $C_8H_9O_3SNa$ requires Na, 11·38 per cent. Ag, 36·24. $C_8H_9O_3SAg$ requires Ag, 36·64 per cent.).

3: *3'-Dimethyl-4 : 4'-dimethoxydiphenyldisulphone.*—A mixture of the sodium salt of the above sulphinic acid (3 g.) and 2-methoxytoluene-5-sulphonylchloride (3 g.) in 20 c. c. absolute alcohol was boiled for 5 minutes and diluted with water. The flocculent precipitate was crystallised from benzene, m. p. 206·5° (decomp.). This is identical with the insoluble product (*A*) described in the preceding paragraph. (Found: C, 51·54; H, 5·05; S, 17·45. $C_{16}H_{18}O_6S_2$ requires C, 51·89; H, 4·66; S, 17·3 per cent.).

3: *3'-Dimethyl-4 : 4'-dimethoxydiphenyldisulphoxide.*—The disulphide (*vide* below) (4 g.), in 30 c. c. glacial acetic acid was oxidised by a 30% solution of hydrogen peroxide ($1\frac{1}{2}$ mol.) and the mixture set aside for 24 hours when stout needles, m. p. 118°, were obtained (yield, 3 g.). Evidently the substance (*B*, see above) formed by the spontaneous decomposition of 2-methoxytoluene-5-sulphinic acid must be a disulphoxide since the mixed m. p. of these two compounds did not change. (Found: C, 56·68; H, 5·55; S, 18·9. $C_{16}H_{18}O_4S_2$ requires C, 56·1; H, 5·35; S, 18·93 per cent.).

2-Methoxy-5-thioltoluene was prepared by the reduction of the corresponding sulphonyl chloride with zinc dust and dilute hydrochloric acid in the usual way. The colourless oil, extracted by ether from the steam-distillate, was purified by distillation (b. p. 236-237°) which then immediately solidified; m. p. 42-43°. (Found: C, 61·88; H, 6·74; S, 21·19. $C_8H_{10}OS$ requires C, 62·34; H, 6·49; S, 20·78 per cent.).

3: *3'-Dimethyl-4 : 4'-dimethoxydiphenyldisulphide.*—The above thiophenol (3·5 g.) was dissolved in 75 c. c. *N*-sodium hydroxide and

a solution of iodine (7.5 g.) in potassium iodide was gradually added with shaking. The disulphide separated as oily drops which gradually solidified (yield, 8 g.). It formed pale yellow thick crystals from alcohol, m. p. 44-45°. (Found: C, 62.59; H, 6.05; S, 21.3. $C_{16}H_{18}O_2S_2$ requires C, 62.74; H, 5.88; S, 20.98 per cent.).

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